

Excess molar volumes and viscosity deviations in binary mixtures of *N,N*-dimethylacetamide with formamide and *N,N*-dimethylformamide at 298.15, 308.15 and 318.15 K[†]

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Densities and viscosities of the binary mixtures of *N,N*-dimethylacetamide with formamide and *N,N*-dimethylformamide have been measured at 298.15, 308.15 and 318.15 K. The excess molar volumes (V^E) and the viscosity deviations ($\Delta\eta$) of the mixture from the ideal mole fraction rule have been calculated from these data. The values of both V^E and $\Delta\eta$ have been discussed in terms of intermolecular interactions between the mixing components of the binary mixture. The computed results have been fitted to the Redlich-Kister polynomial relation to estimate the regression coefficients and standard errors for these systems.

Amides are very interesting compounds and they possess the very common in nature donor-acceptor -CO-NH- peptide bond and display the property of self-association by the H-bond¹. Further, tertiary amides offer great interest because they are related to structural problems in molecular biology. This led us to investigate the excess properties of the mixtures of *N,N*-dimethylacetamide (DMA) with familiar solvents formamide (FA) and *N,N*-dimethylformamide (DMF) because DMA is a good model of a peptide bond. DMA is a dipolar aprotic solvent and due to the moderate dielectric constant ($\epsilon = 37.8$ at 298.15 K) it is likely to be moderately structured². On the other hand, formamide mainly consists of the chain-like hydrogen bonded structure by combining through -NH₂.....O=CH- interactions³ and its dielectric constant and dipole moment ($\epsilon = 109.5$ and $\mu = 3.86$ D at 298.15 K)⁴ are very high. DMF manifests no significant intermolecular H-bonding ability⁵ and has moderate dielectric constant and high dipole moment ($\epsilon = 36.71$ and $\mu = 3.86$ D at 298.15 K)⁶. Thus a systematic study of the structural and energetic consequence of the interactions between DMA and FA and between DMA and DMF will enable us to understand how primary and tertiary amides exercise thermodynamic and kinetic control over the chemical activities of peptide bonds in another tertiary amide, i.e. *N,N*-dimethylacetamide. In the present study, we have tried to explore the sensitivity of the composition dependence of the excess molar volume (V^E) plus viscosity deviations ($\Delta\eta$) of liquid mixtures containing the amide functional group which constitute an important tool in the interpretation of com-

plex molecules of biological interest.

Results and discussion

The densities, viscosities, excess molar volumes and viscosity deviations of *N,N*-dimethylacetamide + formamide mixture and *N,N*-dimethylacetamide + *N,N*-dimethylformamide mixture as a function of mole fraction of *N,N*-dimethylacetamide at 298.15, 308.15 and 318.15 K are presented in Tables 1 and 2, respectively. The excess functions have been calculated using the equations,

$$V^E = V - (v_1x_1 + v_2x_2) \quad (1)$$

$$\Delta\eta = \eta - (\eta_1x_1 + \eta_2x_2) \quad (2)$$

where V and η are the respective solution properties and v_1

Table 1. Experimental density (ρ), absolute viscosity (η), excess molar volume (V^E) and viscosity deviation ($\Delta\eta$) for the binary mixtures of *N,N*-dimethylacetamide with formamide at different temperatures

x_1	ρ g cm ⁻³	η mPa s	V^E cm ³ mol ⁻¹	$\Delta\eta$ mPa s
	Temp. = 298.15 K			
0.0000	1.1254	2.953	0.000	0.000
0.0350	1.1120	3.217	-0.044	0.335
0.0700	1.0997	3.457	-0.091	0.646
0.1110	1.0866	3.656	-0.149	0.928
0.1500	1.0752	3.822	-0.204	1.172
0.2053	1.0606	3.966	-0.272	1.428
0.2414	1.0518	3.971	-0.323	1.506
0.3009	1.0387	3.932	-0.402	1.587
0.3563	1.0275	3.789	-0.463	1.556

[†]Dedicated to Professor R. P. Rastogi.

Table-1 (contd.)

0.4177	1.0162	3.537	-0.517	1.428
0.4580	1.0092	3.338	-0.544	1.310
0.5011	1.0021	3.094	-0.564	1.153
0.5474	0.9948	2.826	-0.575	0.979
0.5972	0.9873	2.530	-0.569	0.783
0.6500	0.9797	2.251	-0.548	0.611
0.7092	0.9717	1.916	-0.505	0.395
0.7500	0.9663	1.720	-0.462	0.282
0.7948	0.9607	1.540	-0.404	0.192
0.8910	0.9492	1.210	-0.242	0.057
1.0000	0.9371	0.933	0.000	0.000
Temp. = 308.15 K				
0.0000	1.1118	2.384	0.000	0.000
0.0350	1.1045	2.532	-0.051	0.203
0.0700	1.0923	2.677	-0.104	0.403
0.1110	1.0791	2.847	-0.164	0.637
0.1500	1.0677	2.950	-0.224	0.800
0.2053	1.0522	3.037	-0.304	0.974
0.2414	1.0442	3.057	-0.354	1.050
0.3009	1.0307	3.027	-0.424	1.113
0.3563	1.0195	2.920	-0.484	1.093
0.4177	1.0080	2.741	-0.544	1.010
0.4580	1.0011	2.594	-0.575	0.926
0.5011	0.9940	2.430	-0.600	0.830
0.5474	0.9867	2.235	-0.615	0.707
0.5972	0.9791	2.028	-0.609	0.578
0.6500	0.9715	1.812	-0.584	0.445
0.7092	0.9632	1.579	-0.532	0.305
0.7500	0.9578	1.441	-0.482	0.231
0.7948	0.9522	1.289	-0.429	0.148
0.8910	0.9406	1.035	-0.268	0.046
1.0000	0.9283	0.819	0.000	0.000
Temp. = 318.15 K				
0.0000	1.1072	1.951	0.000	0.000
0.0350	1.0944	2.077	-0.070	0.169
0.0700	1.0826	2.180	-0.140	0.315
0.1110	1.0700	2.286	-0.221	0.471
0.1500	1.0590	2.357	-0.299	0.590
0.2053	1.0446	2.416	-0.397	0.716
0.2414	1.0361	2.420	-0.459	0.764
0.3009	1.0228	2.389	-0.541	0.806
0.3563	1.0117	2.310	-0.609	0.795
0.4177	1.0001	2.160	-0.660	0.720
0.4580	0.9930	2.076	-0.686	0.686
0.5011	0.9859	1.953	-0.707	0.616
0.5474	0.9785	1.810	-0.715	0.529
0.5972	0.9709	1.650	-0.706	0.430
0.6500	0.9632	1.505	-0.678	0.350
0.7092	0.9550	1.316	-0.623	0.233
0.7500	0.9795	1.205	-0.564	0.172
0.7948	0.9437	1.096	-0.492	0.118
0.8910	0.9318	0.901	-0.291	0.041
1.0000	0.9193	0.726	0.000	0.000

Table 2. Experimental density (ρ), absolute viscosity (η), excess molar volume (V^E) and viscosity deviation ($\Delta\eta$) for the binary mixtures of *N,N*-dimethylacetamide with *N,N*-dimethylformamide at different temperatures

X_1	ρ g cm ⁻³	η mPa s	V^E cm ³ mol ⁻¹	$\Delta\eta \times 10^2$ mPa s
Temp. = 298.15 K				
0.0000	0.9436	0.802	0.000	0.000
0.0500	0.9433	0.809	-0.009	-0.012
0.1062	0.9429	0.816	-0.016	-0.025
0.1500	0.9426	0.822	-0.021	-0.034
0.2171	0.9421	0.831	-0.025	-0.046
0.2600	0.9418	0.837	-0.027	-0.051
0.3094	0.9414	0.843	-0.029	-0.057
0.3500	0.9411	0.849	-0.031	-0.060
0.4050	0.9407	0.856	-0.032	-0.063
0.4550	0.9404	0.863	-0.033	-0.064
0.5042	0.9400	0.870	-0.034	-0.065
0.5500	0.9397	0.876	-0.034	-0.063
0.6071	0.9393	0.883	-0.033	-0.060
0.6550	0.9389	0.890	-0.032	-0.056
0.7140	0.9385	0.898	-0.030	-0.051
0.7500	0.9383	0.903	-0.028	-0.047
0.7968	0.9379	0.909	-0.025	-0.041
0.8500	0.9375	0.916	-0.020	-0.032
0.9112	0.9370	0.925	-0.013	-0.020
0.9500	0.9368	0.930	0.007	-0.012
1.0000	0.9364	0.937	0.000	0.000
Temp. = 308.15 K				
0.0000	0.9348	0.713	0.000	0.000
0.0500	0.9345	0.718	-0.008	-0.017
0.1062	0.9341	0.724	-0.014	-0.034
0.1500	0.9338	0.729	-0.018	-0.045
0.2171	0.9332	0.737	-0.023	-0.059
0.2600	0.9330	0.742	-0.025	-0.065
0.3094	0.9326	0.747	-0.027	-0.072
0.3500	0.9323	0.752	-0.029	-0.077
0.4050	0.9319	0.758	-0.030	-0.081
0.4550	0.9316	0.763	-0.031	-0.083
0.5042	0.9313	0.769	-0.032	-0.084
0.5500	0.9309	0.774	-0.032	-0.081
0.6071	0.9305	0.781	-0.031	-0.079
0.6550	0.9302	0.786	-0.030	-0.074
0.7140	0.9298	0.793	-0.028	-0.069
0.7500	0.9295	0.797	-0.026	-0.064
0.7968	0.9292	0.803	-0.023	-0.056
0.8500	0.9288	0.809	-0.018	-0.043
0.9112	0.9284	0.816	-0.012	-0.028
0.9500	0.9281	0.820	-0.006	-0.017
1.0000	0.9277	0.826	0.000	0.000
Temp. = 318.15 K				
0.0000	0.9256	0.638	0.000	0.000
0.0500	0.9253	0.642	-0.006	-0.022

Table-2 (contd.)

0.1062	0.9249	0.647	-0.012	-0.043
0.1500	0.9246	0.652	-0.016	-0.056
0.2171	0.9242	0.658	-0.021	-0.072
0.2600	0.9239	0.662	-0.023	-0.080
0.3094	0.9235	0.666	-0.026	-0.088
0.3500	0.9233	0.670	-0.027	-0.094
0.4050	0.9229	0.675	-0.028	-0.099
0.4550	0.9226	0.679	-0.029	-0.101
0.5042	0.9223	0.684	-0.030	-0.102
0.5500	0.9219	0.688	-0.030	-0.100
0.6071	0.9216	0.694	-0.029	-0.097
0.6550	0.9213	0.698	-0.028	-0.093
0.7140	0.9209	0.704	-0.026	-0.086
0.7500	0.9206	0.707	-0.024	-0.080
0.7968	0.9203	0.712	-0.021	-0.071
0.8500	0.9199	0.717	-0.017	-0.055
0.9112	0.9196	0.723	-0.011	-0.036
0.9500	0.9193	0.727	-0.006	-0.022
1.0000	0.9189	0.732	0.000	0.000

and v_2 and η_1 and η_2 are the molar volumes and the viscosities of the pure components. The molar volume V is defined by the relation,

$$V = \frac{M_1x_1 + M_2x_2}{\rho}$$

where M_1 and M_2 are the molecular masses of pure substances and ρ is the density of the mixture.

Graphical representations of V^E and $\Delta\eta$ as functions of mole fraction of DMA are given in Figs. 1 and 2, respectively.

The excess properties V^E were fitted to the Redlich-Kister equations⁷,

$$V^E = x_1(1 - x_1) \sum A_j(1 - 2x_1)^j \quad (3)$$

where A_0, A_1, A_2 are adjustable parameters. These parameters were evaluated by fitting $V^E/x_1(1 - x_1)$ to eqn. (3) by the method of least-squares. The values of these parameters

Fig. 1. Variation of excess molar volume of the binary mixtures of *N,N*-dimethylacetamide (a) with formamide and (b) with *N,N*-dimethylformamide at 298.15 (●), 308.15 (■) and 318.15 K (▲).

Fig. 2. Variation of viscosity deviations of the binary mixtures of *N,N*-dimethylacetamide (a) with formamide and (b) with *N,N*-dimethylformamide at 298.15 (●), 308.15 (■) and 318.15 K (▲).

along with the standard deviation $\sigma(Y^E)$ of Y^E as defined by the equation,

$$\sigma(Y^E) = [\sum (Y_{obs}^E - Y_{cal}^E)^2 / (N - M)]^{0.5} \quad (4)$$

are recorded in Table 3. In eqn. (4), N is the total number of points and M is the number of parameters.

Excess molar volume :

The systems DMA + FA and DMA + DMF show negative V^E values over the entire range of mole fraction and over the range of temperatures studied (Fig. 1). Such trends in V^E values have been observed in other systems also. Though both the systems show minima at a mole fraction of about 0.55 of DMA but the substitution of H by

CH_3 at the N-site in *N,N*-dimethylformamide caused a noticeable effect on the V^E values which may be explained qualitatively by postulating the two opposing set of contributions : (i) expansion due to dipole-dipole interactions of the unlike components of amide mixtures and size differences and (ii) contraction due to multiple hydrogen bonding between unlike molecules of the mixture or self-association of the components. The actual value would be the balance between the two opposing effects. However, the experimental results suggest that the latter effect is more prominent than the former. The value of V^E in case of formamide mixture is much more negative than in DMF mixture. This indicates that primary amide has a greater

H-bonding ability than tertiary amide in amide-amide mixtures. The steric hindrance of the two methyl groups of DMF⁸ makes DMF weaker in hydrogen bonding ability than formamide which has a capability of three hydrogen bond donors and three acceptors¹. From Fig. 1 we see that as the temperature increases, the V^E values become more negative in formamide system but in DMF system the result becomes reversed. The decrease of V^E with the increase in temperature is explained by considering the difference in the molar volumes of the two liquids at different temperatures. The difference in the molar volumes of DMA and FA is 52.94 cm³ mol⁻¹ at 298.15 K while its value at 318.15 K is 54.08 cm³ mol⁻¹. This shows that as the temperature of the mixture increases, the difference in the molar volumes of the two liquids also increases, but the smaller sized molecules of FA easily fit⁹ into the voids created by larger molecules of DMA resulting in less increase in the volume of the mixture with increase of temperature. In case of DMF mixtures, the difference in the molar volumes of DMA and DMF is very low, i.e. 15.56 cm³ mol⁻¹ at 298.15 K, so the interstitial accommodation of one component into the other is ruled out. A rise in temperature leads to the breaking of hydrogen bonded structures between unlike molecules and thus the dipole-dipole interactions of the unlike components make the V^E values less negative compared to lower temperature.

Viscosity :

The experimental viscosities as a function of mole fraction of DMA for both the systems are given in the Tables 1 and 2. The broad maxima observed in case of FA + DMA mixture at about 0.25 mole fraction of DMA suggest high association or complex formation between formamide and

DMA. On the other hand, the viscosities of DMF + DMA system increase almost linearly without any maxima or minima with an increase in the DMA content in the mixture. The absence of any maxima in the intermediate composition gives an indication of the possible absence of specific interaction between DMF and DMA.

Viscosity deviations :

The DMA + FA system exhibits a sharp positive deviation of $\Delta\eta$ over the entire mole fraction range and over the three temperatures investigated (Fig. 2) with maxima corresponding to a mole fraction of about 0.3 in DMA. Such trends are also observed in DMA + ME and DMA + H₂O systems. These $\Delta\eta$ values indicate specific hydrogen bonding interactions between DMA and formamide molecules. This is also supported by the excess molar volume studies as reported above. As the temperature increases, the magnitude of the viscosity deviation sharply decreases due to the rapid breaking up of the hydrogen bonds in the system and ultimately tend to approach ideality.

The DMA + DMF system displays very slight negative deviation of $\Delta\eta$ from ideality over the entire mole fraction range at the studied temperatures. The minima correspond to the mole fraction of about 0.5 of DMA (Fig. 2). Further, with the increase of temperature, $\Delta\eta$ values become more and more negative. The moderately structured DMA seems to undergo a structure-breaking effect when mixed with DMF, similar to *N*-methylacetamide's behavior with DMF¹⁰. Apart from this, dispersion and dipolar forces between these two aprotic and unlike solvents may also give rise to negative $\Delta\eta$ values. Such negative deviations from ideality were also

Table 3. Coefficients of eqn. (3) and the standard deviations

Function	Temp. K	A_0	A_1	A_2	A_3	A_4	$\sigma(F)$
<i>N,N</i> -Dimethylacetamide + formamide							
V^E (cm ³ mol ⁻¹)	298.15	-0.0025	-1.1334	-1.9690	4.8761	-1.7709	0.0005
	308.15	-0.0041	-1.2927	-1.6146	4.4368	-1.5255	0.0011
	318.15	0.0001	-2.0253	-0.1598	3.3254	-1.1380	0.0006
$\Delta\eta$ (mPa s)	298.15	-0.0470	12.0894	-27.7521	18.0097	-2.2704	0.0066
	308.15	-0.0488	8.2506	-18.0947	10.6810	-0.7675	0.0056
	318.15	-0.0210	5.9409	-13.1388	8.0087	-0.7775	0.0029
<i>N,N</i> -Dimethylacetamide + <i>N,N</i> -dimethylformamide							
V^E (cm ³ mol ⁻¹)	298.15	-0.0010	-0.1771	0.3763	-0.4151	0.2179	0.0001
	308.15	-0.0005	-0.1582	0.3019	-0.3017	0.1592	0.0001
	318.15	-0.0001	-0.1383	0.2260	-0.1884	0.1010	0.0001
$\Delta\eta$ (mPa s)	298.15	0.0000	-0.0028	0.0034	-0.0007	0.0002	0.0001
	308.15	0.0000	-0.0037	0.0051	-0.0027	0.0013	0.0001
	318.15	0.0000	-0.0047	0.0072	-0.0052	0.0026	0.0001

observed in propylene carbonate (PC) + methanol and PC + tetrahydrofuran mixtures¹¹.

So far the results discussed reveal that in the DMA + FA system, strong heteroassociation is present through multiple hydrogen bonding between the polar groups of the unlike molecules. Also large negative V^E and large positive $\Delta\eta$ values of this system are indicators for this phenomenon. On the other hand, there is a weak dipole-dipole interaction and a slight structure-breaking effect in the DMA + DMF mixture as observed from the experimental data.

Experimental

N,N-Dimethylacetamide (DMA, SRL, India) was shaken with charged CaO (A.R., B.D.H.) for 1–2 h, then decanted and distilled twice; the middle fraction was collected and used. Its density ($0.93644 \text{ g cm}^{-3}$) and viscosity (0.93700 mPa s) at 298.15 K compared well with the literature values which are 0.9366 g cm^{-3} and 0.919 mPa s , respectively⁶. Formamide (E. Merck, >99%) was dried over freshly ignited quicklime for several hours and then distilled over reduced pressure and the purified solvent had a density of 1.1254 g cm^{-3} at 298.15 K and viscosity of 2.9527 mPa s at 298.15 K. *N,N*-Dimethylformamide (E. Merck) was kept overnight with phosphorus pentoxide, then decanted and distilled over nitrogen. The purified solvent had a density of $0.94362 \text{ g cm}^{-3}$ and viscosity of 0.80240 mPa s at 298.15 K. All these values are in good agreement with the literature values⁶.

Densities were measured with an Ostwald-Sprengel type pycnometer having a bulb volume of about 25 cm^3 and an internal diameter of the capillary of about 1 mm. The pycnometer was calibrated at 298.15, 308.15 and 318.15 K with triple-distilled water and benzene. The reproducibility of the density measurement was $\pm 3 \times 10^{-5} \text{ g cm}^{-3}$. The

temperature of the thermostatic water-bath was controlled to $\pm 0.01 \text{ K}$ of the desired temperature.

The kinematic viscosities were measured by means of a suspended-level Ubbelohde viscometer with a flow of about 539 s for distilled water at 298.15 K. The time of efflux was measured with a stopwatch capable of recording $\pm 0.1 \text{ s}$. The viscometer was always kept in a vertical position in a water-thermostat controlled to $\pm 0.01 \text{ K}$. The estimated error of the viscosity measurements was $\pm 0.2\%$. In all cases, the experiments were performed at least in five replicates for each composition and at each temperature and the results averaged.

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